

Rotational motion estimation and analysis in digital image sequences

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Abstract

In this paper we consider the problem of motion estimation, analysis and selective reconstruction of objects undergoing rotational motion. There are multiple objects rotating with different angular velocities in the image sequences. The goal is to estimate their distinct motion parameters (in this case is the angular velocities), and also identify their locations at each time instance by selective reconstruction. These parameters and locations can be used for various purpose such as motion compensation in video coding, military target detection, recognition and tracking, robot's focus/shift attention, road navigation, etc. The new algorithm we have developed is based on angular velocity tuned 2D+T filters. One of the important fact about our algorithm is that it is effective for both spinning motion and orbiting motion, thus unifies the treatment of the two kinds of rotational motion. Furthermore, it can also derives the angular velocities separately by choosing different scale values once the objects have different sizes. The algorithm is robust against noise and occlusion. It is simulated and tested on several synthesized image sequences corrupted by noise and shows to be accurate.

1 Introduction

The motion we are studying here is rotational motion. It has been classified into two types according to their rotational axis. If the axis is the center of gravity on the object, it is called spinning. If the axis is outside the object, it is called orbiting. The signal we worked on is 2D+T digital image sequences. We extend the work [6] such that it works fine for both spinning motion and orbiting motion, thus makes no difference in dealing with the two kinds of rotational motion.

In order to identify motion parameters, we tune the 2D+T filters to angular velocity, spatial scale, spatial

orientation, spatial and temporal translations. They behave as matched filters and can perform minimum-mean-square error (MMSE) estimation of motion parameters. This approach is fundamentally different from other techniques proposed in the literature such as those based on gradient-based optical flow, block matching, pel-recursive, Bayesian model and Markov random field (MRF) model [1][2] [3][4] [5]. It does not need point corresponding techniques or stochastic models. The angular velocities can be robustly obtained for the moving objects even after the sensor is corrupted by noise and the objects have temporary occlusion. It is effective to derive the distinct angular velocities belonging to the rotating objects even when they have the same shape, size and intensity. Furthermore, the angular velocities can be separately detected by using different scales if the rotating objects have different sizes.

2 Rotational velocity tuned filters

In this paper we first introduce the rotational velocity tuned filters which can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_g &= [T_g]\psi(\vec{x}, t) \\ &= a^{-1}\psi(a^{-1}R(\theta_0 + \theta_1(t - \tau))(\vec{x} - \vec{b}))\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where the parameters of interest in our case are the angular velocity θ_1 , the spatial translation $\vec{b} \in \mathbf{R}^2$, the temporal translation $\tau \in \mathbf{R}$, the scale $a \in \mathbf{R}_+ \setminus \{0\}$ and the spatial orientation $\theta_0 \in [0, 2\pi)$, where $R(\theta_0) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_0 & -\sin \theta_0 \\ \sin \theta_0 & \cos \theta_0 \end{pmatrix}$ and $g = \{\vec{b}, \tau, a, \theta_0, \theta_1\}$.

The $\psi(\vec{x}, t)$ we chose behaves as an bandpass filter, its 2D+T version in frequency domain is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\psi}(\vec{k}, \omega) &= \hat{\psi}(\vec{K}) \\ &= |\det(D)|^{\frac{1}{2}} \begin{pmatrix} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\vec{K} - \vec{K}_0)^T D (\vec{K} - \vec{K}_0)} \\ -e^{-\frac{1}{2}\vec{K}_0^T D \vec{K}_0} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\vec{K}^T D \vec{K}} \end{pmatrix}\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where the hat $\hat{\cdot}$ stands for Fourier transform. $\vec{K} = (\vec{k}, \omega)^T \in \mathbf{R}^2 \times \mathbf{R}$, $\vec{k}, \omega$ are spatial and temporal coordinates in frequency domain. $\vec{K}_0 = (k_{0x}, k_{0y}, \omega_0)^T$, D is a positive definite matrix. For $2D + T$ signals, $D = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \epsilon_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \epsilon_t \end{pmatrix}$, where the ϵ factors introduce anisotropy in the filter shape.

To match filters with the signal, take inner product of the tuned filters ψ_g and the 2D+T signal, which can be written in frequency domain as:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{\psi}_g | \hat{s} \rangle &= \langle \hat{\psi}_{\vec{b}, \tau, a, \theta_0, \theta_1} | \hat{s} \rangle \\ &= \int_{\mathbf{R}^2 \times \mathbf{R}} d^2 \vec{k} d\omega [T_g \hat{\psi}] (\vec{k}, \omega) \bar{\hat{s}} (\vec{k}, \omega) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where the overbar $\bar{\cdot}$ stands for the complex conjugate.

3 Motion Estimation and selective reconstruction algorithm

The algorithm allows us to derive the motion parameters and perform selective reconstruction robustly and accurately. we treat the spinning and the orbiting the same except considering that they may have different scale.

In order to derive the angular velocities, we use ψ_g as the tuning filters. Let us fix the scale $a = a_n$:

$$e(\theta_1) = \sum_{\theta_0} \sum_{\vec{b}} \sum_{\tau} | \langle \hat{\psi}_{\vec{b}, \tau, a=a_n, \theta_0, \theta_1} | \hat{s} \rangle |^2 \quad (4)$$

For a single rotating object with angular velocity θ_1^* from $e(\theta_1)$ (Figure 1) we get a series of peaks corresponding to the multiples of the actual angular velocity θ_1^* , which are $n\theta_1^*$, $n = 0, 1, \dots, M$, where $M = \left\lfloor \frac{2\pi}{\theta_1^*} \right\rfloor - 1$, $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ means taking the integer part. We can obtain the θ_1^* by taking $n=1$, i.e, the angular velocity corresponding to the second peak.

For multiple rotating objects, for example, two objects, one with angular velocity θ_{11}^* , the other θ_{12}^* , we obtain a series of peaks corresponding to $n_1\theta_{11}^*$ and $n_2\theta_{12}^*$, where $n_1 = n = 0, 1, \dots, M1$, $M1 = \left\lfloor \frac{2\pi}{\theta_{11}^*} \right\rfloor - 1$, $n_2 = n = 0, 1, \dots, M2$, $M2 = \left\lfloor \frac{2\pi}{\theta_{12}^*} \right\rfloor - 1$. If θ_{11}^* and θ_{12}^* are not too far apart, we can obtain them by taking the angular velocities corresponding to the second and third peaks.

Furthermore, if the two rotating objects have different sizes of their shapes, we can separately derive their own angular velocities by selecting different scales in equation 4.

To reconstruct image at a selected time instance $\tau = \tau_n$ with rotational motion θ_1^* , the algorithm is as followed:

$$I(\vec{b}) = \sum_{\theta_0} | \langle \hat{\psi}_{\vec{b}, \tau=\tau_n, a=a_n, \theta_0, \theta_1=\theta_1^*} | \hat{s} \rangle |^2 \quad (5)$$

The location of the object corresponds to the peaks in $I(\vec{b})$.

4 Rotational motion analysis

Let $s(\vec{x})$ be the still 2D signal, its Fourier transform is $\hat{s}(\vec{k})$. Its rotating version can be expressed as $\tilde{s}(\vec{x}, t) = s(R(\theta_1^*(t))(\vec{x} - \vec{b}^*))$, where θ_1^* is the angular velocity and $\vec{b}^*$ is the position of the rotational axis, it determines whether the rotation is a spinning or an orbiting. If $\vec{b}^*$ lies outside the object, it is orbiting, if it is on the object, it is spinning.

The Fourier transform of the $\tilde{s}(\vec{x}, t)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\tilde{s}}(\vec{k}, \omega) &= \int_{\mathbf{R}^2 \times \mathbf{R}} d^2 \vec{x} dt s(R(\theta_1^* t)(\vec{x} - \vec{b}^*)) e^{-i(\vec{k} \cdot \vec{x} + \omega t)} \\ &= e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{b}^*} \int_{\mathbf{R}^2 \times \mathbf{R}} d^2 \vec{y} dt s(\vec{y}) e^{-i(\vec{k} \cdot R^T(\theta_1^* t) \vec{y} + \omega t)} \\ &= e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{b}^*} \int_{\mathbf{R}} dt \hat{s}(R(\theta_1^* t) \vec{k}) e^{-i\omega t} \end{aligned}$$

We can see no matter it is spinning or orbiting motion, the expression is the same for both cases in our algorithm. Also, $\hat{s}(R(\theta_1^* t) \vec{k})$ is the Fourier transform of the 2D still signal rotating with angular velocity θ_1^* . A special case is when $\theta_1^* = 0$, $\hat{\tilde{s}}(\vec{k}, \omega) = e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{b}^*} \hat{s}(\vec{k}) \delta(\omega)$, this reduces to the still image. In general, $\theta_1^* \neq 0$, in order to integrate out with respect to t, we can use polar coordinate in frequency domain. i.e, let $\vec{k} = (\rho \cos \phi, \rho \sin \phi)^T$, and denote $\hat{s}(\vec{k}) = f(\rho, \phi)$, so,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{s}(R(\theta_1^* t) \vec{k}) &= \hat{s}(\rho \cos(\theta_1^* t + \phi), \rho \sin(\theta_1^* t + \phi)) \\ &= f(\rho, \theta_1^* t + \phi) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\tilde{s}}(\rho, \phi, \omega) &= e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{b}^*} \int_{\mathbf{R}} dt f(\rho, \phi + \theta_1^* t) e^{-i\omega t} \\ &= \frac{e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{b}^*}}{\theta_1^*} \int_{\mathbf{R}} d\phi' f(\rho, \phi') e^{-i\omega \frac{(\phi' - \phi)}{\theta_1^*}} \\ &= \frac{e^{-i\vec{k} \cdot \vec{b}^*}}{\theta_1^*} e^{i\frac{\omega \phi}{\theta_1^*}} \hat{f}\left(\rho, \frac{\omega}{\theta_1^*}\right) \end{aligned}$$

5 Simulation results

We have tested our algorithm for both spinning motion (Figures 2) and orbiting motion(Figures 7) corrupted by noise.

To obtain the angular velocities, take the inner product as described in equation 4. In the spinning case, from Figure 3, we can derive a series of peaks corresponding to $n_1 * \frac{\pi}{4}$ and $n_2 * \frac{\pi}{3}$ within $[0, 2\pi)$, $n_1 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 7, n_2 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 5$. The actual angular velocities correspond to the 2nd and 3rd peaks, i.e, $\theta_{11}^* = \pi/4$ and $\theta_{12}^* = \pi/3$. The two objects have different sizes, so using different scale a , we can further separate the two angular velocities apart (Figure 4 and 5). It is the same with the orbiting motion. The peaks in Figure 8 correspond to $n_1 * \frac{\pi}{4}$ and $n_2 * \frac{\pi}{6}$ within $[0, 2\pi)$, $n_1 = 0, 1, \dots, 7, n_2 = 0, 1, \dots, 11$. The actual angular velocities correspond to the 2nd and 3rd peaks, i.e, $\theta_{11}^* = \pi/4$ and $\theta_{12}^* = \pi/6$.

In order to obtain the location of the objects at each time instance, we can reconstruct the objects undergoing the motion (Figures 6), which enable us to obtain its location by detecting the peaks of the intensity in the reconstructed images. This step can be performed for all the τ , which enable us to derive a trajectory of the moving objects. It can be used for tracking and other purpose.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we are developing a new method to achieve motion estimation for rotational motion. The method is original in the sense that it is effective for both orbiting and spinning motion and it is based on spatio-temporal angular velocity tuned filters that provide angular velocities and location of all the discontinuities embedded in the digital image sequences. The technique has been shown to be robust against image noise and occlusion. Further studies will develop matched filter method to optimally estimate, track, segment and reconstruct moving object according to their actual rotational motion parameters in 3D+T obtained from their projections on the 2D+T image sequences.

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Figure 1: The angular velocity estimation. The actual image sequence is a single object undergoing spinning motion with spinning axis (33,33) and angular velocity $\theta_1^* = \pi/4$ (noise is added). The y-axis of this graph is $e(\theta_1)$ calculated according to equation 4. The unit of the x-axis is degree. The eight peaks correspond to $n * \pi/4$ (i.e, $45^\circ n$) within $[0, 2\pi)$, $n = 0, 1, \dots, 7$.

Figure 2: The first image from image sequences with two objects undergoing spinning motion. One object with spinning axis at (8,33) and angular velocity $\theta_{11}^* = \pi/4$. The other's spinning axis is at (33,16), its angular velocity $\theta_{12}^* = \pi/3$. Noise is added.

Figure 3: The angular velocity estimation, the peaks correspond to $n_1 * \frac{\pi}{4}$ and $n_2 * \frac{\pi}{3}$ within $[0, 2\pi)$, $n_1 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 7, n_2 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 5$. The actual angular velocities correspond to the 2nd and 3rd peaks, i.e. $\theta_{11}^* = \pi/4$ and $\theta_{12}^* = \pi/3$.

Figure 4: The function $e(\theta_1)$ when tune the filters to a small scale, what we get is the angular velocity of the smaller sized object. The eight peaks correspond to $n * \pi/4$ (i.e. $45^\circ n$) within $[0, 2\pi), n=0, 1, \dots, 7$. We can see in this way, we further separate the motion parameters belonging to different rotating objects.

Figure 5: The function $e(\theta_1)$ when tune the filters to a large scale. what we get is the angular velocity of the larger sized object. The six peaks correspond to $n * \pi/3$ (i.e. $60^\circ n$) within $[0, 2\pi), n=0, 1, \dots, 5$.

Figure 6: The reconstructed image for the second image from the image sequences

Figure 7: The first image from the image sequences with two objects undergoing orbiting motion. One has orbiting center at $(30, 28)$ which is outside of the object, its angular velocity $\theta_{11}^* = \pi/4$. The other's orbiting center is at $(20, 20)$, its angular velocity $\theta_{12}^* = \pi/6$. Noise is added.

Figure 8: The angular velocity estimation. The peaks correspond to $n_1 * \frac{\pi}{6}$ and $n_2 * \frac{\pi}{4}$ within $[0, 2\pi)$, $n_1 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 11, n_2 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 7$. The actual angular velocities correspond to the 2nd and 3rd peaks, i.e. $\theta_{11}^* = \pi/6$ and $\theta_{12}^* = \pi/4$.